

Innovative Dementia Care: Exploring the Dementia Village Model from an International Perspective

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Background: The rising global prevalence of dementia highlights critical gaps in conventional care models and calls for innovative, person-centered approaches. One such concept gaining attention is the dementia village—an integrated, community-like environment that rethinks how care for people with dementia (PwD) is delivered.

Objective: This study explores the dementia village model from an international perspective, focusing on its core characteristics, benefits and limitations, staff roles, and implications for further development.

Methodology: Guided expert interviews (n=8) were conducted with international and national facility managers and researchers experienced in dementia village design and operation. Participants ranged in age from 29 to 71 years (median: 62.5), with six identifying as female. Qualitative content analysis was conducted following Kuckartz and Rädiker. The material was independently coded by two researchers; divergences were reviewed through discussion, leading to a revision of the coding definitions.

Outcome: Dementia villages are typically characterized by open, spacious grounds that resemble small-scale neighborhoods, featuring street networks, green spaces, and buildings with residential and communal functions such as cafés and shops. These settings aim to de-institutionalize care and promote a sense of normality and autonomy.

The care model emphasizes small household units and a person-centered approach, with a strong focus on enabling independence and prioritizing freedom over strict safety measures. Target groups generally include individuals with moderate to severe dementia requiring structured support. The built and social environments are perceived to have a mitigating effect on challenging behaviors.

The work environment is described as highly flexible, though often lacking clear structures and standardized routines. In staff recruitment, interpersonal competencies and soft skills are considered more important than formal qualifications. The evaluation of dementia villages, while still in its early stages, and the assessment of quality is strongly influenced by ethical considerations and broader societal debates about the desirability and purpose of dementia care.

Implication for research: The study highlights that the impact of dementia villages is highly dependent on contextual implementation. This underlines the need for careful planning that integrates environmental, social, and organizational elements while considering ethical implications. Despite increasing interest in the model, robust scientific evaluation remains limited. Future research should adopt both qualitative and quantitative indicators, aligned with established care quality frameworks and oriented towards the conventional standards applied in nursing homes.

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